

PAS stained kidney from 18 week old WKY (normotensive line related to SHR lines)

PAS stained kidney from 18 week old SHR-B2

PAS stained kidney from 18 week old SHR-A3

PAS stained kidney from 40 week old SHR-B2

PAS stained kidney from 40 week old SHR-A3

PAS stained kidney from 40 week old SHR-A3(Trip B2)

PAS stained kidney from 40 week old SHR-A3-IGHKO